

Evaluating the impact of different agropastoral practices on wind erosion in western Sahel

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Abstract :

In the Sahel, nutrient-poor sandy soils are vulnerable to wind-driven erosion and can be further degraded if left unprotected. As more than 60% of the Sahelian population depends on rainfed agriculture, land degradation is a primary concern. In the last 60 years, climatic and socio-economic factors have thoroughly modified the Sahelian cropping systems. Understanding the interaction between land uses, agropastoral practices and wind erosion is crucial.

The aim of this study is to estimate the effect of the main types of land uses and management that occurred in the Senegalese groundnut basin in the last decades on potential wind erosion at the field scale. *In-situ* measurements of weather, vegetation and horizontal fluxes of aeolian sediments were monitored on typical land uses (groundnut plot, four fallows, four millet plots), each with contrasting and representative land managements, creating an unprecedented dataset in this region. We developed a modeling approach combining vegetation models with a horizontal flux model, calibrated on the gathered data. This modeling approach was able to reproduce previous measurements and can be used on un-instrumented plots.

Measurements of horizontal fluxes on the plots ranged from 538.7 kg.m⁻¹.year⁻¹ on bare soil to almost no flux on fallows. Simulations accurately represent the dynamics and order of magnitudes of erosive events despite having a strong sensibility to the aerodynamic roughness length. The comprehensive simulation of the impact of groundnut, millet with and without residues and fallows on potential wind erosion highlights the impact of dry vegetation cover, especially weeds, after the rainy season.

Keywords: Wind Erosion, Sahel, Senegal, Land Uses, Agricultural practices

48 1. Introduction

49

50 Wind-driven erosion causes fine particles from the topsoil to be transported to their immediate surrounding
51 (creeping, saltation) or into the atmosphere (suspension). It is a threshold phenomenon: a horizontal flux of
52 sediments is generated when wind speed exceeds a threshold value depending on soil surface characteristics.
53 Once over the threshold, the flux intensity is determined by both wind speed and soil surface characteristics
54 (Bagnold, 1941). Those can be non-erodible elements increasing roughness of the surface (such as crop residues)
55 as well as the soil grain size distribution and its cohesion, which can be impacted by soil moisture or crusting
56 (Iversen and White, 1982; Fryrear and Skidmore, 1985; Raupach et al., 1993). Wind erosion can deteriorate soil
57 structure and water holding capacity while removing organic matter and nutrients (Sterk, 2003).

58

59 In the Sahel, located south of the Saharan desert and defined by the north-south gradient of precipitation ranging
60 from 200 to 600 mm (Lebel and Ali, 2009), more than 60% of the population lives in rural area and depends on
61 rainfed agriculture for subsistence and income (OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and
62 Development) and Sahel and West Africa Club, 2014). The rainy season, which lasts from July to October, is
63 critical for vegetation development and determines the state of the soil cover for the following dry season, when
64 green vegetation turns into straw and litter. During the long dry season, unprotected soils are vulnerable and can
65 be strongly affected by wind erosion (e.g., Bielders et al., 2004). In central Sahel, the start of the monsoon (May-
66 June) is accompanied by strong winds due to mesoscale convective systems (MCS) while the vegetation cover
67 is at its lowest, generating most of the annual wind-driven erosion (Bielders et al, 2004; Bergametti et al., 2020).
68 This is different in the western Sahel where in-situ observations showed that wind erosion occurs from February
69 to June, and is caused by winds just above the erosion threshold (Pierre et al., 2023).

70

71 Some estimates have been made of soil displacement caused by saltation, especially in central and eastern Sahel,
72 ranging from net positive values in fallows due to dust deposition (Rajot, 2001) to net losses of 25 to 50 t.ha⁻¹
73 ¹.y⁻¹ in southwestern Niger fields (Bielders et al., 2000, 2001). This movement of matter and nutrients can
74 generate local or regional land degradation, especially when occurring in already nutrient poor soils such as in
75 arid and semi-arid areas (Mainguet and Chemin, 1991; Visser and Sterk, 2007; Doso, 2014). As an example,
76 Sterk et al. (1996) quantified nutrient losses by wind in a millet field in southwestern Niger. The content of
77 carbon and nutrients (potassium, nitrogen and phosphorus) lost in the displaced sediments was near the
78 necessary nutrient uptake of a millet field for a year, as a loss of 57.1 kg.ha⁻¹ K, 79.6 kg.ha⁻¹ C, 18.3 kg.ha⁻¹ N
79 and 6.1 kg.ha⁻¹ P was estimated.

80

81 In the last 60 years, cropping systems in the Sahel changed due to climatic and socio-economic factors
82 (Lericollais, 1970; Badiane et al., 2000; Brandt et al., 2014). This led in some places to a large expansion of
83 croplands to the detriment of natural land covers. For instance, in Burkina Faso, land used for rainfed agriculture
84 grew from 15 percent of the country surface in 1975 to 39 percent in 2013 (Tappan et al., 2016). In Senegal,
85 total agricultural land area remained stable in that period due to the expansion of croplands in central Senegal
86 while northwestern croplands were abandoned (Pires, 2012; Tappan et al., 2016). Before the 1960's in the
87 groundnut basin, the main agricultural region of Senegal, plots were organized following at least a 3-year
88 rotation of millet, groundnut, and fallowing (Buldgen et al., 1993). However, the growing pressure on
89 agricultural land has been at the expense of fallows, used to regenerate soil nutrients (Freeman, 1982), and as a
90 result fallows surface drastically decreased since 1960 (Masse et al., 2018).

91

92 These changes of land uses and practices have a direct effect on land degradation (loss of natural areas, no
93 nutrient restoration through fallowing). However, intensification and extension of croplands are also thought to
94 play a role in increasing the susceptibility of soil to wind erosion (Lee et al., 2012; Chi et al., 2019), especially
95 in drought prone environments (Lee and Gill, 2015). Studies have shown that the replacement of fallows by

96 cropland increased wind erosion (Rajot, 2001; Pierre et al., 2018), especially if no crop residues are left on field
97 after the harvest (Sterk, 2003; Abdourhamane Touré et al., 2011).

98

99 While this is an important concern for population depending on rainfed agriculture (Biielders et al., 2004), few
100 studies are dedicated to estimate and compare the effect of the main agropastoral practices (e.g., type of crops,
101 fallowing, residue collection, grazing) on wind erosion in the Sahel (Sterk et al., 1996; Rajot, 2001; Biielders et
102 al., 2001; 2002; Abdourhamane Touré et al., 2011; 2019). To our knowledge, modeling wind erosion for
103 different land uses, despite being necessary to assess horizontal flux production caused by change in
104 agropastoral practices at larger scales, has only been attempted in a small number of studies (Visser et al., 2005;
105 Pierre et al, 2014; 2015; 2018), especially for pastoral areas and millet fields.

106

107 Thus, the objective of this study is first to estimate through in situ measurements the effect of different
108 representative agropastoral practices on flux generation at a plot level. Secondly, this study aims to develop a
109 modeling approach capable of reproducing the horizontal flux generation on un-instrumented plots. We present
110 here a complete and unique dataset of weather conditions, vegetation characteristics and aeolian sediment fluxes
111 for traditional (1950-1960) and modern agropastoral practices in western Sahel (Senegalese groundnut basin),
112 as well as a combination of vegetation development and flux generation models capable to accurately reproduce
113 the observed results. Section 2 introduces the in-situ experiments and the different models used in the study.
114 The field measurements, calibration and results of the modeling approach are presented in section 3 and
115 discussed in section 4. Section 5 summarizes the main conclusions of the study.

116

117 **2. Material and methods**

118 **2.1. Study sites**

119

120 We monitored sites in the groundnut basin in Sahelian Senegal (14-16.5° in latitudes) as testing grounds for
121 investigating the impact of historical Sahelian agricultural practices and their trajectory in the last 60 years on
122 wind erosion (Fig. 1). For 4 years, 9 plots were instrumented (1 plot of groundnut for 2 years, 4 fallows for one
123 year, and 4 plots of millet for one year, each plot size being approximately 1 ha). For each, we monitored
124 weather conditions, vegetation growth, and horizontal flux of sediments.

125

126 The groundnut and millet plots are located in Bambey (14°43'16.84''N, 16°29'26.95''W), on the grounds of
127 the Senegalese Institute of Agricultural Research (ISRA/CNRA). The groundnut plot (GN0) was monitored
128 from February 2020 to January 2022. To estimate maximum potential flux over unprotected soil and bare soil
129 properties, the field was cleared and plowed in early 2020 (Fig. 2a), leaving a homogenous and smooth surface.
130 Measurements from February 2020 to June 2020 thus depict the response of bare soil to wind erosion.
131 Groundnut was cultivated during the rainy seasons of 2020 (Fig. 2 b, c) and 2021. The millet plots comprise the
132 plot previously used for groundnut completed by three other adjacent plots. Millet (Souna variety) was
133 cultivated on the four plots (1.5 ha) from June 2023 to June 2024. The four millet plots were planned to differ
134 in management in order to reproduce regional and historical practices: M1 was manually seeded and crop
135 residues were left on the field after harvest (Fig. 2e, h), M2 was seeded with the help of animal traction, and
136 crop residues were collected during the harvest (Fig. 2 f, i). M3 and M4 were respectively the same as M1 and
137 M2 but millet was intercropped with cowpea (seeded between millet rows) on both of these plots, and cowpea
138 was fully harvested before the millet harvest (Fig. 1).

139

Figure 1 : {Map of Senegal & study sites}. Left : Map of Senegal. The Groundnut Basin (in yellow) and the Ferlo (in green) compose the Sahelian Senegal. The two study sites are located in the Diourbel region of the groundnut basin (red dots). Right : Drone photography of studied fallows (top) and millet plots (bottom). (Credit : Jean-Louis Rajot)

140 The fallows are located 10 km north of Bambey near the village of Ndem (14°48'25.95''N 16°28'9.42''O).
 141 Four adjacent fallows were monitored from July 2022 to June 2023 (Fig. 2 d, g). The four fallows were chosen
 142 because they differ in age and cover type: F1 is a new fallow with residues from the previous year's millet crop,
 143 F2 is an older fallow (>2 years) covered in part by *Guiera senegalensis*, a typical Sahelian bush, F3 is a new
 144 fallow where groundnut and cowpea were cultivated the year before, and F4 is an older fallow with a higher
 145 tree density.

146

147 All plots were instrumented with 5 two dimensional sonic anemometers at 1.9, 1.5, 1, 0.6, and 0.2 m (WindSonic
 148 TM Gill Instruments Ltd), and temperature sensors (1.6, 1.2, 0.7, 0.4, 0.03 m) mounted on the same mast placed
 149 downwind, and on each site a rain gauge (ARG100 Tipping Bucket, 0.2 mm precision, Campbell® Scientific
 150 company for GN0, Environmental Measurements Ltd for other plots), a solar radiation sensor (CMP11, Kipp
 151 and Zonen), and a saltiphone (Eijkelkamp, Spaan and Van den Abeele, 1991) to measure sand grain impacts
 152 and identify erosion events were placed. These data are measured every 10 seconds and averaged (cumulated)
 153 at a 5-minute resolution for wind and solar radiation (for precipitations and saltiphone). To measure wind-blown
 154 sediments, 5 masts of 5 MWAC sand traps (Modified Wilson And Cooke, Sterk and Raats, 1996), placed at 5,
 155 10, 20, 40, and 80 cm on each mast, were installed on all plots and were collected every two weeks dried and
 156 weighed with 1 mg precision. To ensure the measurement of only the sediments originating from the plots, on
 157 fallows 3 masts of 5 MWAC were located downwind while two others were located on the borders to capture
 158 ingoing sediment from neighboring plots. On millet and groundnut plots, all 5 MWAC masts were located
 159 downwind (ie., southwestern corner). On millet plots, grass strips were grown around each plot to ensure that
 160 no outside flux of sediment is entering the plot. From the measurements of sediment mass at different heights,
 161 horizontal flux was computed by fitting an exponential equation as proposed by Fryrear and Saleh (1993).

162

163 On the groundnut plot vegetation was monitored with height, cover (through photographs following the
 164 methodology described in Appendix A), and biomass (destructive) measurements during the 2021 rainy season
 165 while weed biomass measurements were taken during the dry season. On fallows and millet plots, vegetation
 166 was monitored for the whole year. Height measurements and photographs of vegetation cover were done weekly
 167 along two diagonal transects for each plot, and biomass classification and destructive weighing for 6 1x1m²
 168 (0.9*1.8 m² on millet plots) random locations across each plot were done monthly (every two weeks during the
 169 rainy season for millet plots). The size and frequency of the sampling are described in Appendix A.

Figure 2: {Pictures of study sites} a-c) Pictures of the groundnut plot in February 2020 when the soil is almost bare, September 2020 during the cropping period and December 2020 after the harvest when weeds occupy a large part of the plot. d-g) Pictures of the fallows from fallow F1 in September 2022 (d) and late November 2022 (g). e,f,h,i) Pictures of millet plots M1, M4 in September 2023 (e and f) and January 2023 (h and i) where residues are seen on M1.

170
 171 During the monitoring of the groundnut plot, 1.2% of the data was lost due to solar-powered battery
 172 malfunctioning, mostly between 10 to 25 June 2020, 01 to 12 June 2021, and sporadically between 01 and 21
 173 August 2021. Temperature sensors 1 (lowest sensor), 2 and 5 malfunctioned for longer periods of time leading
 174 to the loss of respectively 20%,10% and 14% of their data on different periods.

175 While the instruments were set up between the 5th and 14th of July 2022 on the fallows, the temperature sensors
 176 started operating between the 20th and 21st of July. The higher temperature sensor on the millet plot M4 was
 177 defective between the 19th and 27th of July 2023. No other significant missing data is reported during the
 178 monitoring. Part of the data of the groundnut plot was presented in Pierre et al. (2023). Complementary
 179 meteorological data (wind speed, air temperature, relative humidity, precipitation amount) from the INDAAF
 180 (International Network to study Deposition and Atmospheric composition in AFrica) station in Bambe
 181 (Marticorena et al., 2021) were used for gap-filling of missing data.

182

183 Rainy season start and duration were established using methodology from Sivakumar (1988) in which the onset
 184 of the rainy season is defined as the date when at least 20 mm of rain has fallen in 3 consecutive days and no
 185 dry spell longer than 7 days happens in the following 30 days, and the end of the rainy season is defined as the
 186 date after September 1 after which no rain occurs during a period of 20 days. The mean annual rainfall in
 187 Bambeý was calculated using data collected by the CNRA of Bambeý at a daily timescale.

188
 189 A grain size distribution analysis was made for the groundnut plot (which became M4 in 2023) and is used as
 190 the reference soil in this study. This soil is locally known as Dior soil, which is made of almost 95% sand (Table
 191 1).

192

193 2.2. Aerodynamic roughness length estimation method

194

195 The aerodynamic surface roughness z_0 is a key parameter to understand and model the generation of horizontal
 196 flux, as it determines the wind friction velocity and the threshold friction velocity, i.e. the interaction between
 197 the atmosphere and the soil surface.

198

199 In neutral atmospheric conditions, the wind profile is logarithmic (Priestley, 1959) :

200

$$201 \quad u(z) = \frac{u_*(t)}{k} \ln\left(\frac{z}{z_0(t)}\right) \text{ for } z \gg z_0(t) \text{ with } u_*(t) \text{ the wind friction velocity.}$$

202

(1)

203

Soil fraction	Coarse sand	Fine sand	Coarse loam	Fine loam	Clay
Median %	34.95	58	2.8	0.15	4.2
Standard deviation	4.97	4.59	0.77	0.45	0.89

Table 1 : {Grain size analysis} Grain size analysis of the GN0 plot, median and standard of 16 1m² soil surface measurements

204 It is then possible to estimate, in neutral conditions, the aerodynamic roughness length and the wind friction
 205 velocity using only the measured wind profile. In natural conditions, the atmosphere is neutral around sunrise
 206 and sunset and is either stable or unstable during the rest of the day, yielding to an estimate of a z_0 time series
 207 that relies on a restricted number of values. Using the Similarity Theory from Monin and Obukhov (1954), one
 208 describes the wind velocity $u(z)$ in non-neutral conditions:

209

$$210 \quad u(z) = \frac{u_*}{k} \left[\ln\left(\frac{z}{z_0}\right) - \Psi_m\left(\frac{z}{L}\right) + \Psi_m\left(\frac{z_0}{L}\right) \right] \text{ with } L = \frac{u_*^2 \theta}{kg\theta_*}$$

211

(2)

212 Where L is the Monin-Obukhov length (m), Ψ_m is a "stability function", m for momentum and h for temperature,
 213 θ the potential temperature (K) and θ_* the temperature scale.

214 Ψ_m and Ψ_h depend on atmospheric conditions, which are determined by the stability parameter z/L , which is
 215 lower than 0 in unstable conditions and greater than 0 in stable conditions. Following the iterative fitting
 216 procedure developed by Frangi and Richard (2000) and adapted by Marticorena et al. (2006), the parameters
 217 u_* , z_0 , θ_* and L can be determined, as well as Ri the Richardson number, which describes the turbulence of the
 218 flow and is a function of the stability parameter :

219

$$220 \quad Ri = \frac{g}{T} \frac{\partial \theta / \partial z}{(\partial u / \partial z)^2}$$

222 Where g is the acceleration of gravity (9.81 m.s^{-2}), T the absolute air temperature (K). Low absolute Ri values
223 correspond to conditions close to neutrality.

224

225 We adapted the method from Marticorena et al. (2006) in order to produce a z_0 time serie containing only the
226 best reliable z_0 estimates. By defining neutrality thresholds on the Richardson number ($|Ri| < 0.005$, $|Ri| < 0.02$,
227 $|Ri| < 0.2$) and a minimum density of z_0 values for a given time period (set at 30 values in 15 days), we devised
228 a denoising method that respects both the demand for reliable z_0 values (low $|Ri|$ values) and homogenous and
229 dense z_0 time series. z_0 values are only kept in the time serie if they fit the strongest Richardson threshold
230 possible ($|Ri| < 0.005$) while also meeting the density criteria. The resulting time series represent an estimation
231 of the aerodynamic roughness length z_0 at a 15 minutes resolution.

232

233 2.3. Modeling Approach

234

235 Extensive measurements on experimental plots were made to estimate horizontal fluxes on varying land uses
236 and managements representative of different agropastoral practices in the last 60 years in western Sahel. This
237 dataset is unprecedented to our knowledge in Senegal. To allow for flux estimation in area without precise in-
238 situ measurements, we also combined vegetation development and horizontal flux models calibrated on our
239 dataset (Fig. 3).

240

241 Weather data (*in-situ* measurements, climate re-analysis or projections), soil features and agropastoral practices
242 specificities, are used as inputs to a vegetation model. A different vegetation growth model is used for rangeland
243 (STEP, Sahelian Transpiration Evaporation and Productivity model, Mougin et al., 1995) and cropland (STICS,
244 Simulateur mulTIdisciplinaire pour les Cultures Standard, Brisson et al., 2003), both simulating vegetation
245 biomass, height, and cover. These outputs are then used to estimate the aerodynamic roughness length z_0 , a key
246 parameter for aeolian horizontal flux modeling. Both the the aerodynamic roughness length z_0 and the weather
247 and soil data are inputs to the horizontal flux model (DPM, Dust Production Model, Marticorena and Bergametti,
248 1995). This approach was used in previous studies in Niger and Mali for a narrower range of conditions and
249 allowed for an accurate simulation of the horizontal flux (Pierre et al., 2014; 2015).

250

251 2.3.1. Vegetation Models

252

253 The STEP model is designed to simulate the herbaceous vegetation development and degradation in Sahelian
254 conditions. At a daily timescale, the STEP model describes the soil water budget and vegetation growth based
255 on the site meteorology (rainfall, temperature, humidity, radiation, and wind speed) and characteristics (soil
256 composition and profile, grazing pressure, C3/C4 proportions). It has shown a good ability to reproduce
257 observed biomass in previous studies (Tracol et al., 2006; Pierre et al., 2015; Mougin et al., 2019). The model
258 consists of two submodels describing 1) water budget and 2) vegetation growth and senescence. During the dry
259 season, the dynamics of straws and litter biomass are calculated through the effect of meteorological factors and
260 trampling or ingestion by grazing animals (Delon et al., 2015; Pierre et al., 2015; 2016). Soil productivity is
261 implicitly taken into account in the model through the conversion efficiency input ϵ (g/MJ). Finally, the STEP
262 model provides LAI (Leaf Area Index), dry matter biomass of green, straws and litter, and the fraction of soil
263 covered by vegetation at a daily time step.

264

265 STICS is a dynamic soil-crop model working at a daily time-step. It is based on several modules simulating
266 processes such as crop growth, yield formation, carbon, water and nitrogen transfer and balances (Brisson et al.,

267 2003). This model was chosen for its ability to simulate different crops and practices, as well as its robustness
 268 in different climates: it accurately represented crops in tropical or semi-arid conditions such as sorghum-cowpea
 269 intercropping (Traoré et al., 2022), groundnut, millet (Sow et al., 2024) or rice (Ranaivoson et al., 2022).
 270
 271 The model require inputs similar to STEP for weather and soil conditions. It also requires field management
 272 information such as sowing date, depth and density, fertilization, irrigation and additional practices. Finally,
 273 plant parameters, specifying phenological stage durations, leaf growth and harvested organs details are need. In
 274 this study, we use a groundnut parametrization presented in Appendix B and millet parametrization from Sow
 275 et al. (2024). Because STICS does not handle plant degradation after harvest, an additional module was used
 276 for this purpose (Appendix C).
 277

Figure 3 : {Modeling approach description} Diagram of the modeling approach. Gray boxes are inputs, light green boxes are models and orange boxes are model outputs

278 2.3.2. Horizontal Flux Model

279

280 The DPM has been used to estimate horizontal flux of aeolian sediments at the plot scale in the Sahel in previous
 281 studies (Pierre et al., 2014; 2015; 2018). A brief description of its functioning is given in this sub-section.

282 Wind erosion occurs when wind friction velocity exceeds a threshold value. This threshold is a function of the
 283 state of the soil surface and of the presence of non-erodible elements such as pebbles or vegetation. The wind
 284 drag is partitioned between erodible and non-erodible parts of the soil. This is taken into account through the
 285 aerodynamic roughness length z_0 in the DPM model. Once the threshold is exceeded, the wind erosion is a
 286 power function of the wind friction velocity.

287 The wind friction velocity threshold u_{*t} is described as follows:

$$288 \quad u_{*t}(z_0, z_{0s}) = \frac{u_{*ts*}}{f_{eff}(z_0, z_{0s})} \quad (4)$$

291 Where u_{*ts} is the wind friction velocity threshold over bare soil, z_0 (z_{0s}) the aerodynamic roughness length of
 292 the surface (bare soil) and f_{eff} the efficient fraction velocity ratio :

$$293 \quad f_{eff}(z_0, z_{0s}) = 1 - \frac{\ln\left(\frac{z_0}{z_{0s}}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{\delta}{z_{0s}}\right)}, \quad \frac{\delta}{z_{0s}} = a * \frac{X^p}{z_{0s}}$$

295 (5)

296 δ is the height of the Internal Boundary Layer, and a , X , and p were determined as $a = 0.7$, $X = 0.4$ m, and $p =$
 297 0.8 in previous studies for vegetated surfaces with good agreement with observations (Elliot, 1958; Darnenova
 298 et al., 2009; Pierre et al., 2014). The horizontal flux G is then described as:

299

300 if $u_*(t) > u_{*t}(t)$:

$$301 \quad G(t) = E * \frac{\rho_a}{g} * u_{*t}(t)^3 * \left(1 + \frac{u_{*t}(t)}{u_*(t)}\right) \left(1 - \left(\frac{u_{*t}(t)}{u_*(t)}\right)^2\right),$$

302 else $G(t) = 0$

303 (6)

304 And the wind friction velocity $u_*(t)$ defined in Eq.1

305

306 With z the wind measurement height, E is the erodible fraction ratio (i.e., the soil proportion not covered by
 307 obstacles), ρ_a the air density ($1.227 * 10^{-3}$ kg.m⁻³). E is taken from vegetation models daily outputs and is adjusted
 308 based on weekly photo interpretation as the models tend to underestimate soil cover with a constant bias. $u(z)$
 309 is the wind speed at height z , $k=0.4$ the Von Karman constant.

310

311 Values of z_{0s} and u_{*ts*} are linked to bare soil properties of the cropped plot. We used measurements made
 312 between March and May 2020 on GN0 as it was representative of bare soil. z_{0s} was estimated based on the
 313 lowest median daily z_0 values of the plot, reaching values between $1.5 * 10^{-4}$ and $3 * 10^{-4}$ m (z_0 time series
 314 estimation method is described in section 2.2). These values are consistent with other methods of
 315 z_{0s} determination based on coarsest grain size diameter (D_{coarse}). Indeed, z_{0s} can be estimated as a function of
 316 D_{coarse} as the following:

317

$$318 \quad z_{0s} = \frac{D_{coarse}}{30} \quad (\text{Marticorena et Bergametti, 1995; Laurent et al. 2006}) \quad \text{or} \quad z_{0s} = 2 \frac{D_{coarse}}{30} \quad (\text{Farrel and Sherman,}$$

319 2006).

320

321 Based on the grain size distribution of the plot, 30% of the soil is made of coarse sand (Table 1), which can
322 range from 0.2 to 2 mm in diameter. This way, z_{0s} range from $6.7 \cdot 10^{-6}$ m to $1.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$ m.

323

324 u_{ts^*} estimation was made using Abdourhamane Touré et al. (2011) methodology, also used in Pierre et al.
325 (2023). For each month, the u_* value for which the saltiphone had a 50% chance of activation was computed.
326 The value corresponded to a monthly estimation of u_{t^*} , and u_{ts^*} if the soil is bare. We found u_{ts^*} values ranging
327 from 0.20 m/s to 0.24 m/s, which is consistent with the value of 0.22m/s for sandy bare soil in Abdourhamane
328 Touré (2011).

329 For the following, we chose to set z_{0s} between $1.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ m and $3 \cdot 10^{-4}$ m with steps of $0.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ m and u_{ts^*}
330 between 0.20 m/s and 0.24 m/s with steps of 0.005 m/s to account for uncertainty in the bare soil surface
331 characteristics.

332

333 The horizontal flux G is in kg/m/s, which corresponds to the amount of sediments crossing a 1-meter-wide and
334 infinitely high vertical plane perpendicular to the wind direction during that time period. For a 1 ha field, 1kg/m
335 equals 0.1 t/ha losses assuming wind is perpendicular to a 100m side of the field and that no sediment is entering
336 the field.

337

338 To account for soil moisture, the simulated horizontal flux was inhibited during rain events and during 12h
339 following the event, based on previous studies relying on pluriannual observations from Central Sahel
340 (Bergametti et al., 2016).

341

342 To compare each land use/management, it is necessary to disentangle the role of wind speed and the role of the
343 soil surface cover. To do so, a ratio G_{DUP} of the total horizontal flux generated during the erosive season G to
344 the associated cumulated Dust Uplift Potential (Marsham et al., 2011; Pierre et al., 2023) has been devised.

345

$$346 \quad G_{DUP}(z) = \frac{G}{DUP(z)} * 1000 \quad (7)$$

347

348

349 Where $DUP(z) = u(z)^3(1 + \frac{u_t(z)}{u(z)})(1 - \frac{u_t(z)^2}{u(z)^2})$ for $u > u_t$, and 0 otherwise. The DUP was calculated at $z = 1.9$ m
350 and threshold wind speed $u_t(z)$ was set at 5 m.s^{-1} using the methodology described in Abdourhamane Touré et
351 al. (2018). The DUP is unaffected by vegetation cover, thus G_{DUP} allows for comparison horizontal fluxes,
352 regardless of the year of measure.

353

354 **3. Results**

355

356 **3.1. Field measurements**

357

358 A significant dataset was acquired from these experiments. As in situ measurements in the Sahel are scarce,
359 such a comprehensive record of weather, vegetation and horizontal flux for several land uses and management
360 is rather unique in the literature to our knowledge.

361

362 **3.1.1. Meteorological measurements**

363

364 Annual rainfall, start and length of rainy season are shown in Table 2. Compared to the 1999-2019
365 precipitations, three out of four years are under the mean, 2021 and 2023 being the driest years (almost 60mm
366 -or 10%- less than the mean), 2022 being the only study year with rainfall larger than the mean. However, each

367 year of the study is either near (2023) or above the median rainy season duration. Though annual rainfall is the
 368 key driver for crop production in the Sahel (Guan et al., 2015), the duration of the rainy season and the onset
 369 of the rainy season seem to play a large part in crop yield formation (Zhang et al., 2018). With a late onset of
 370 the rainy season and low annual rainfall, the groundnut and millet plots were growing in degraded conditions in
 371 2021 and 2023. Millet plots even needed to be resowed due to a dry spell after early rains (not shown).

Site (year)	Annual rainfall (mm)	Rainy season length (days)	Rainy season start
Bare soil (2020)	546	108	July 11
Groundnut (2021)	507.2	99	July 31
Fallows (2022)	649.6	120	July 20
Millet (2023)	506.6	86	August 11
<i>Mean Bambey (1999-2019)</i>	562	87	<i>July 24</i>

Table 2: {Rainfall summary} Rainfall summary for all sites and mean for 1999-2019 (Total annual rainfall, rainy season duration and start)

372
 373 Figure 4 presents the monthly average wind speed and direction at 1.9m and precipitation on the groundnut,
 374 fallow (F1) and millet (M4) plots. Wind followed three consecutive patterns each year. First, from November
 375 to February, the harmattan blew from the north-northeast (330-60°). Then, during spring and summer, winds
 376 from the northwest region (330°) increased as their overall speed increased and other winds decreased (65% of
 377 winds coming from the 330° direction occurred between February and June, 95% of winds over 3.5 m/s coming
 378 from the 330° direction occurred between February and June). Wind speed reached a monthly average maximum
 379 value in April (3.3m/s) while most strong winds (>7.5 m/s) during the dry season were recorded in February.
 380 Finally, at the start of the summer, wind speed got overall milder during the rainy season (mean dry season: 2.5
 381 m/s, mean rainy season: 1.6 m/s) with the onset of the West African Monsoon as wind began blowing from the
 382 southwest (240°). While mean wind speed decrease from the onset of the rainy season until its minimum in

Figure 4 : {Monthly climate summary on the study sites}. Monthly weather data from 4 years of records (Feb 2020-Jan 2022, June 2022-July 2024). Mean monthly precipitation are presented in blue bars, monthly aggregated 5 min measurement of winds speeds at 1.9m are shown in grey boxplots and monthly wind roses on the top.

383 October (0.8 m/s), this is also when convective events set the maximum recorded wind speed. All instances of
 384 winds over 10 m/s were recorded between June and August, most of the events happening in July. These strong
 385 events, despite having the strongest erosive potential, were less frequent than erosive winds from February to
 386 April and were less able to generate a flux as they were accompanied by rains and the soil was often covered
 387 by vegetation at this point. Recorded winds over fallows were lower than on the fields but the intra-annual
 388 dynamic remained the same (not shown).

389
 390 **3.1.2. Vegetation characteristics**

391
 392 Comparison of total sampled biomass for each type of crop/land cover is shown in Figure 5. Even on cropped
 393 plots where multiple weeding occur, the weed biomass was not neglectable as it can reach over 50 g/m² on
 394 millet field. There is an offset between the start of the rainy season and the start of the growing period. Early
 395 rains before the start of the rainy season can trigger the growth of weeds which are removed through weedings

Figure 5 : {Vegetation biomass monitoring}. Measured biomass (in g/m²) on each type of crop and plot.

396 during the early stage of cropping.
 397 Maximum biomass reached on average 140 g/m² on millet plots, 150 g/m² on fallows and 60 g/m² on the
 398 groundnut plot. On all plots, the maximum biomass was reached before the end of the rainy season (usually 70
 399 to 80 days after the start of the rainy season). After this peak, vegetation slowly degraded over the course of the
 400 dry season reaching biomass ranging from 5 g/m² for the dry season 2020 weeds to 29 g/m² for the millet crop
 401 residues on M1. Degrading factors include trampling and grazing from animals, as well as biotic
 402 (microorganisms) and climatic degradation. Weeds degraded faster than crop residues such as millet stems.

403
 404 **3.1.3. Horizontal flux**

405
 406 Figure 6 report the recorded horizontal fluxes. 90% of the horizontal flux was generated between February and
 407 July. Winds in the early erosive season (February to April) on GN0 in 2020 were especially strong compared to
 408 winds on the same plot in 2021 (not shown). After the 2020 harvest, the plot was left as is and some weeds
 409 provided a small cover to the soil as they degraded over the dry season. This combination of factors explains
 410 how the horizontal flux was divided by more than 2 between 2020 (538.7 kg/m) and 2021 (194.3 kg/m) (Tab.
 411 3).

412

Figure 6: {Recorded Horizontal fluxes} Recorded horizontal fluxes all plots

413 Fallow vegetation is, by definition, not harvested and its degradation is only influenced by weather and grazing
 414 livestock. Despite livestock grazing, the soil remained protected most of the year, and the horizontal flux was
 415 non-negligible only at the very end of the dry season (sediments collected on May 11, May 29, and June 20)
 416 (Fig. 6c). Very low annual amounts of sediments were collected on each fallow (<6.1 kg/m/yr; Tab. 3).
 417 However, the collected samples suggest that the various characteristics of fallows played a role in generating
 418 horizontal flux. The older fallows (F2: Old fallow with bushes, F4: Old fallow with trees) and the protected
 419 young fallow (F1: new fallow with millet residues) were indeed less affected by wind erosion (F4: 1.8 kg/m,
 420 F2: 2.0 kg/m, F1: 2.0 kg/m; Tab. 3) than the new unprotected fallow (F3: 6.1 kg/m; Tab. 3).
 421

Site (year)	Recorded horizontal flux (kg/m, Feb-July)			
Bare soil (2020)	538.70 +/- 62.14			
Groundnut (2021)	194.34 +/- 56.19			
Fallows (2022)	1.98 +/- 0.79	1.97 +/- 1.51	6.07 +/- 0.94	1.75 +/- 0.55
Millet (2023)	61.57 +/- 11.69	169.4 +/- 23.33	23.59 +/- 3.06	145.81 +/- 34.49

Table 3 : {Annual horizontal fluxes} Annual recorded horizontal fluxes on each plot and number of measurements with non-negligible sediment mass (15 days between each sample collection). For fallows and millet measurements are from plot 1 to 4 going from left to right.

422 Measurements of the horizontal flux on millet plots seem to further confirm the role of millet residues on wind
 423 erosion mitigation (Abdourhamane Touré et al., 2011; Pierre et al., 2018). Indeed, horizontal flux on millet plots
 424 where residues were not collected (M1, M3) was 2 to 7 times lower than on millet plots with residue collection
 425 (M2, M4) (Tab. 3). This phenomenon got stronger as weeds degraded on all fields and the only soil protection
 426 remaining was prone millet stems during the end of the dry season (Fig. 6d). On millet he yearly horizontal flux
 427 ranged from 23.6 to 169.4 kg/m (Tab. 3), the main driver of difference was the presence of crop residues on the
 428 plots.

429 **3.1.4. Aerodynamic roughness length estimation**

430

431 Using wind profile measurements on each plot, a denoised estimation of aerodynamic roughness length was
432 obtained at a 15 minutes timescale. To catch the smooth signal of the surface characteristics, the z_0 time series
433 was estimated through daily medians. Using this method, a final z_0 time series derived from observations was
434 defined for each plots, with an associated smoothed $z_0(t)$ time serie (30 days rolling median centered on t) used
435 for horizontal flux simulations (Fig. 7).

436

437 On all plots, z_0 values increased during the growing period of the vegetation, ranging from less than a millimeter
438 at the end of June to almost 10 cm in October, at the peak of the rainy season. During the following dry season,
439 the aerodynamic roughness length decreased as the remaining vegetation degraded. Fallows (excepted F4) were
440 more stable than cropped plots, with z_0 values usually between few millimeters and few centimeters, while
441 groundnut and millet plots can reach much lower z_0 values. z_0 values obtained with this method are further
442 discussed in 4.3.

443

Figure 7 : {Observed z_0 time series} Observed z_0 time series for all plots. Dots are daily medians, lines are 30 days rolling medians.

444 **3.2. Modeling approach**

445

446 **3.2.1. Biomass simulation**

447

448 For the GN0 plot simulation, the output from the crop model STICS shows a strong overestimation (Fig. 8) of
 449 the aboveground biomass as it reaches over 300 g/m² for each simulated year, while the maximum observed
 450 biomass for year 2021 was less than 100 g/m² at best. This difference is explained by STICS difficulty to
 451 simulate highly water and nutrient stressed growing conditions, as was the case in this experiment. However,
 452 the phenology of the groundnut was accurately simulated, as fructification and maturity predicted and observed
 453 dates were close (fructification was predicted on September 19 and observed between September 11 and
 454 September 20, maturity was predicted on November 10, right before the actual harvest on November 16).
 455 Weeds on the field were simulated using the STEP model (Fig. 8) and the final biomass was weighted according
 456 to the effective area that could be covered by weeds during the cropping season. We use a RMSE minimizing
 457 optimization method to first set the value of the conversion efficiency parameter ϵ , and then the value of the
 458 grazing pressure, in TLU/km² (Tropical Livestock Unit per km²) which affects the degradation of the plot
 459 vegetation. The final values were 3.102 g/MJ for ϵ and 1.19 TLU/km². This grazing pressure is on the lower
 460 range of Sahelian estimations but is consistent with animal presence over low fertility areas (Turner and

Figure 8: {Groundnut and weed biomass on GN0, observations and simulations} Groundnut and weeds biomass on plot GN0. R² is calculated on the total vegetation biomass.

461 Hiernaux 2002; Pierre et al., 2015; Audouin et al., 2017).

462

463 Following the same method as described for GN0 weeds, individual calibration was made for each fallow,
 464 results are shown in Table 4. ϵ is consistent with what is known of each fallow (F2 and F4 are older fallows,
 465 presumed to be more fertile). Estimated maximum value of grazing pressure for each plot through biomass
 466 optimization was between 2 and 4 TLU/km². The output of the STEP model after calibration is in very good
 467 agreement with observed biomass (Fig. 9), especially for standing (green and dry) biomass. Litter biomass is
 468 slightly underestimated during the beginning of the dry season (from October to February). The degradation
 469 dynamics and proportion between lying and standing biomass is accurately simulated.

470

Fallow	ϵ (g/MJ)	TLU/km ²
F1	2.99	1.99
F2	3.18	2.69
F3	2.91	3.90
F4	3.10	2.79

Table 4 : {STEP Model parameter calibration for fallows} STEP Model parameter calibration for each fallow.

471

472 For each millet plot, vegetation was simulated through the STICS model for millet development and the STEP
 473 model for weed development and degradation (Same as fallows and GN0).The dry millet degradation module
 474 was added to STICS for M1 and M3 where millet residues were left on field. For M2 and M4, nearly all residues
 475 were collected and the only simulated cover after harvest is weeds.

Figure 9: {Vegetation biomass on fallows and Millet plots, observation and simulation} Left : Weed biomass on fallows, standing vegetation is green and litter is brown, Right : Millet (green) and weed (brown) biomass on millet plots. Observations are represented with standard deviations (squares), simulations are represented with a line. R^2 is calculated on the total vegetation biomass.

477 While the values of grazing pressure are in the expected range of values and are consistent with each other (from
 478 2 to 6 TLU/km²), one outlier (20.6 TLU/km² for M1 on weed simulation) is both inconsistent with other values
 479 and the estimated grazing pressure for millet degradation with the dry module. This might be caused by the
 480 stark decrease of weed vegetation on M1 compared to other millet plots, which can also be caused by non-
 481 animal factor such as human interaction. Regarding millet, the STICS model was calibrated through the
 482 modulation of the nitrogen content of the plots to estimate soil fertility. The baseline was established with default
 483 STICS soil nitrogen content (NO₃ ranging from 15 to 20 kg/ha and NH₄ ranging from 4 to 10 kg/ha depending
 484 on soil depth, which is the required N amount for millet culture, Batiano and Ntare, 2000; Kidron et al., 2009)
 485 and was modulated to better fit our observations. Heavy nitrogen stress was necessary to accurately reproduce
 486 the observed biomass, which is consistent with soil measurements made on the plot in 2021, and overall the low
 487 input agriculture of Senegal, especially in the study area.

488

489 Though maximal millet biomass is accurately simulated by STICS, the simulated millet growth is very early in
 490 comparison to our observations. However, this model bias will not affect wind erosion simulation as almost no
 491 horizontal flux is generated during the period of the year in this part of the Sahel.
 492

Millet field	ϵ (STEP)	TLU/km ² (STEP)	TLU/km ² (dry module)	Nitrate modulation (STICS)
M1	3.8	20.6	2	22%
M2	3.3	6.0	No dry module	2%
M3	3.5	3.7	3	0%
M4	2.7	5.6	No dry module	0%

493 Table 5 : {STICS and STEP model parameter calibration for millet plots} STICS and STEP model parameter calibration for millet plots
 494

495 3.2.2. Aerodynamic roughness parametrization

496 For each type of land cover, we use a parametrization linking aerodynamic roughness length z_0 to a vegetation
 497 variable.
 498

499 For herbaceous vegetation growing on fallows and for weeds on crops, we adapted a previous parametrization
 500 from Pierre et al. (2015) designed for rangeland in Central Mali by regressing z_0 values against monthly
 501 observations of vegetation aerial mass. The updated equation is the following:
 502

$$503 z_0 = 0.0003 * B_{standing} + 0.00015 * B_{litter} \quad (8)$$

505 with the biomass B expressed in g.m⁻².

506 For 41 measures, equation 6 gave a R² of 0.65 on our fallow dataset. z_0 parametrizations based on biomass
 507 observations are presented in Figure 10.
 508

509 Similarly, by fitting the biomass measurements of groundnut against the z_0 observations, the following equation
 510 is obtained:
 511

$$512 z_0 = 5.1 * 10^{-4} * B_{groundnut} + z_{0s} \quad (R^2 = 0.76, n=15) \quad (9)$$

515 At the beginning of the growing season, multiple weeding occurred to eliminate the development of competing
 516 herbaceous vegetation. Weeds, however, still developed in the later months of the rainy season (September -
 517 October) and provided the only soil cover after groundnut harvest. At the beginning of the dry season of 2020,
 518 around 40% of the field was still partially occupied by weeds. It is then necessary to consider them when
 519 simulating the z_0 time series outside the groundnut growing season. The relation between weed biomass and
 520 aerodynamic roughness length (Eq. 6) is the same as the one used on fallows. When using the relationship on
 521 the observed weed biomass on the groundnut field during the 2020-2021 dry season, we obtain R²=0.98, for
 522 n=7. The overall parametrization is a maximum between the groundnut and weed parametrization, it scores an
 523 R² of 0.81 for n=24 (Fig. 11).

Figure 10: {z0 parametrization for Fallows and Millet plots} z0 parametrization for fallows (left) and millet plots (right). R² is calculated between all z0 estimations and the median observed value of z0 in a 30-day window around the estimations.

525 Millet parametrizations were proposed in previous studies, linking roughness either to millet height (Pierre et
 526 al., 2015) or biomass (Pierre et al., 2018).

527 Biomass-based parametrization proved to be more efficient in estimating z0 values because biomass is better
 528 correlated to cover density than height. However, the relationship between biomass and roughness changes
 529 before and after the harvest when the millet stems degrade and fall, affecting the value z0 because of changes
 530 in geometry of vegetation cover rather than in its biomass. Also, the development of weeds during and after
 531 cropping plays a non-negligible role in roughness (Bielders et al., 2004).

532 Before harvest, the logarithm of millet biomasses after the exclusion of outlier masses was regressed against the
 533 average z0 value (7-day average centered on measured date).

Figure 11: $\{z_0$ parametrization for GNO} z_0 parametrization compared to observations for GNO. z_0 estimations for groundnut and weeds biomass are respectively derived from equations 8 and 7. R^2 is calculated between all z_0 estimations and the mean observed value of z_0 in a 30-day window around the estimations.

534

$$535 \quad z_0 = 7.1 * 10^{-3} * \ln(B_{millet}) + 2.15 * 10^{-2}$$

536

(10)

537 Where B_{millet} is the total aerial millet biomass.

538

539 After the harvest, the z_0 parametrization takes into account millet residues biomass and herbaceous biomass.

540

$$541 \quad z_0 = 4.4 * 10^{-5} * B_{millet} + 4.7 * 10^{-4} * B_{weeds} + 0.001$$

542

(11)

543 Where B_{weeds} is the total aerial weed biomass.

544

545 Litter cover also affects the roughness z_0 and is considered through the equation proposed in Abdourhamane
546 Touré et al. (2011):

547

$$548 \quad z_0 = 0.0012 \ln(f_{cv}) + 0.0013 \text{ with } f_{cv} \text{ the fraction of soil surface covered by vegetation.}$$

549

(12)

550 The final z_0 value is the maximum between the relevant regressed relation (before or after harvest) and the
551 impact of litter cover, following the methodology described in Pierre et al. (2018).

552 Finally, the R^2 values from this overall parametrization ranged from 0.72 to 0.95, for an overall 0.73 on all plots
553 ($n=56$). The correlation between observed z_0 values and estimated ones from biomass measurements excludes
554 values calculated in September and October as z_0 observations were too scarce during this period to be
555 reliable. A summary of all z_0 parametrization is presented in Table 6.

556

557 3.2.3. Simulated aerodynamic roughness length

558

559 Using the parametrization from 3.2.2. and biomass simulation, we modeled an aerodynamic roughness length
560 time-serie z_{0sim} for the groundnut plot, fallows, and millet plots. Correlation and RMSE between observed and
561 simulated z_0 values are reported in Table 7.

562 For the groundnut plot (GN0), from February to July 2020, the value of z_0 is set to z_{0s} to account for field
 563 clearing. After this date, z_0 is set to the maximum of the z_0 derived from groundnut and the one derived from
 564 weeds biomass. From sowing to harvest, the groundnut cover is the main driver of z_0 , and overestimation of
 565 groundnut biomass thus also leads to an overestimation of z_0 around vegetation maximum (z_0 max 2020 = 36
 566 cm, z_0 max 2021 = 26 cm). After harvest, z_0 is derived from the weeds biomass and a better agreement is found
 567 between observed and simulated z_0 values (Figures are available in Appendix D.). The degradation of weeds
 568 over time allows for a good description of the decline in z_0 values from harvest to beginning of the next rainy
 569 season. Overall, this parametrization gives satisfying results ($R^2=0.69$, $n=680$), especially between January and

Land cover	Used vegetation variable	z_0 estimation method	Equations
Groundnut	Groundnut aboveground biomass (agb), herbaceous agb (standing, litter)	Maximum between function of groundnut biomass and function of weed biomass.	$z_0 = 5.1 * 10^{-4} * B_{groundnut} + z_{0s}$ $z_0 = 0.0003 * B_{standing} + 0.00015 * B_{litter}$ (adapted from Pierre et al. (2015))
Fallows	Herbaceous agb (standing, litter)	Function of weed biomass	$z_0 = 0.0003 * B_{standing} + 0.00015 * B_{litter}$ (adapted from Pierre et al. (2015))
Millet	Millet agb, herbaceous agb (standing litter)	Before harvest, maximum between function of millet aboveground biomass and function soil residues cover After harvest, maximum between function of millet and herbaceous biomass and function of soil residues cover	Before harvest: $z_0 = 7.1 * 10^{-3} * \ln(B_{millet}) + 2.15 * 10^{-2}$ After harvest: $z_0 = 4.4 * 10^{-5} * B_{millet} + 4.7 * 10^{-4} * B_{weeds} + 0.001$ $z_0 = 0.0012 \ln(f_{cv}) + 0.0013$ (Abdourhamane Touré et al., 2011)

Table 6: { z_0 parametrizations for each type of modeled vegetation} Summary of z_0 parametrizations for each type of modeled vegetation. All relations are empirical. Biomass units is in $g.m^{-2}$

570 June 2021 when most of the horizontal flux was generated.

571

572 A strong agreement between observed and simulated z_0 values has been found for fallows with R^2 ranging from
 573 0.81 ($n=317$) to 0.9 ($n=323$). From July to October, the increase of z_0 is explained by vegetation growth. During
 574 the dry season, z_0 is influenced by the decrease of herbaceous biomass and the transformation of standing dry
 575 biomass into litter.

576

577 For the millet plots, the z_0 time-series derived from biomass value are in good agreement with observed z_0 ,
 578 with R^2 values ranging from 0.62 ($n=359$) to 0.88 ($n=335$). Millet growth drives the z_0 increase from July to
 579 October on all plots. After harvest on plots with residue collection (M2 and M4), z_0 's decrease results from
 580 weed biomass degradation. z_0 decreases on M1 and M3 where residues left on field are a combination of millet
 581 stems and weed biomass degradation. On both plot, weeds are the main driver of aerodynamic roughness
 582 evolution until the middle of the dry season (January) and as weeds continue degrading, millet residues take a
 583 more preponderant role. Litter-caused roughness rarely surpasses biomass-caused roughness in our simulations.

584

585

586

587

Plot	GN0	F1	F2	F3	F4	M1	M2	M3	M4
n	680	326	317	325	323	352	335	359	345
R ²	0.69	0.88	0.81	0.89	0.9	0.73	0.88	0.62	0.68
RMSE	0.0974	0.0117	0.0063	0.0040	0.0057	0.0123	0.0092	0.0114	0.0102

Table 7: {Correlation between observed and simulated z_0 }

588

589

590 3.2.4. Simulated horizontal flux

591

592 For horizontal flux simulations, two z_0 time series were used for each plot to validate aerodynamic roughness
 593 length simulation against *in-situ* estimations. z_{0est} was estimated from wind profile as described in 3.1.4. z_{0sim}
 594 was derived from biomass simulations and z_0 parametrizations as described in 3.2.3.

595 Horizontal fluxes during erosive season (February - July) are reported in Table 8 for sand traps observations
 596 and for simulations. Each simulated flux is the mean of the simulations with all values of u_{*tS} (0.20 – 0.24 m/s)
 597 and z_{0s} ($1.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ – $3.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$ m). R² and RMSE are calculated by comparing individual sand trap records with
 598 cumulated simulated flux between two sand trap observations. For fallows and millet fields, averaged results
 599 per land use are also presented to allow for comparison between land uses and practices.

600

601 From February to July 2020, the recorded horizontal flux originated from the bare surface and was representative

Figure 12: {Simulated and observed horizontal fluxes on all plots}. Simulated and observed horizontal fluxes on all plots. Axis on F2 and F4 have been adapted to display the simulated horizontal flux overestimation for z_{0obs} .

602 of the response of a bare soil to wind erosion (Fig. 12a). Both $G(z_{0est})$ and $G(z_{0sim})$ accurately follow the dynamic
 603 of the recorded horizontal flux, with a large event at the end of February 2020, and two erosive periods in April
 604 and in June 2020. Both simulations for the bare surface overestimates the annual flux ($G(z_{0est})$): $653.38 \pm$

605 121.49 kg/m, $G(z_{0sim})$: 746.84 +/- 114.82 kg/m, recorded flux: 538.70 +/- 62.14 kg/m) while remaining in the
606 range of the standard deviation. This is caused by an overestimation of some strong erosive events by the model
607 (22 to 27 February 2020) and simulated yet not observed events in late July 2020 (after seeding) for z_{0sim} caused
608 by the underestimation of early vegetation in the STICS model. Yet, the simulation using z_{0sim} series performs
609 slightly better in terms of R^2 and RMSE (Table 8) than the one using z_{0est} , probably because its smoother
610 dynamics through time is closer to the actual surface characteristics.

611
612 In 2021, the plot was representative of the aftermath of one year of groundnut cropping. In accordance with the
613 measured flux, the simulated horizontal flux is lower than in 2020 ($G(z_{0est})$: 256.19 +/- 81.91 kg/m, $G(z_{0sim})$:
614 122.68 +/- 53.68 kg/m, recorded flux: 194.34 +/- 56.19 kg/m) in similar proportions ($G(z_{0est})$: - 61% from 2020
615 to 2021, $G(z_{0sim})$: - 84%, recorded flux: -64%). The simulation with z_{0obs} performs better before May 2021 as
616 the flux generated using z_{0sim} is underestimated (Fig. 12b). However, horizontal flux recorded after May 2021
617 are accurately simulated by both series. Uncertainty on weed biomass and parametrization between February
618 and June 2021 may play a role in the underestimation of the flux by z_{0sim} . The z_{0sim} time-serie provides a similar
619 RMSE as z_{0est} despite having a worse R^2 score ($R^2_{est} = 0.8$, $R^2_{sim} = 0.56$). For both year and z_0 series, the model
620 is rarely able to simulate very low amounts of horizontal flux (<5 kg/m) as they may happen between September
621 and November.

Name	GN0 (Baresoil)	GN0 (Ground nut)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F	M1	M2	M3	M4	M res	M no res
$G(obs)$	538.70 +/- 62.14	194.34 +/- 56.19	1.98 +/- 0.79	1.97 +/- 1.51	6.07 +/- 0.94	1.75 +/- 0.55	2.94 +/- 2.08	61.57 +/- 11.69	169.4 +/- 23.33	23.59 +/- 3.06	145.81 +/- 34.49	42.58 +/- 26.85	157.6 +/- 16.67
$G(z_{0est})$	653.38 +/- 121.49	256.19 +/- 81.91	0 +/- 1.09	13.3 +/- 30.66	0.35 +/- 3.92	94.95 +/- 48.82	27.15 +/- 45.62	14.46 +/- 24.08	261.73 +/- 90.99	415.36 +/- 116.04	422.72 +/- 111.99	214.91 +/- 283.47	342.23 +/- 113.83
$G(z_{0sim})$	746.84 +/- 114.82	122.68 +/- 53.68	0 +/- 2.12	0 +/- 2.31	0.99 +/- 6.33	0.44 +/- 4.3	0.35 +/- 0.47	0.75 +/- 9.74	109.95 +/- 79.47	66.72 +/- 61.67	203.61 +/- 104.86	33.73 +/- 46.65	156.78 +/- 66.22
R^2 (z_{0est}, Obs)	0.71	0.8	/	0.18	0.08	0.42	0.17	0.32	0.91	0.2	0.3	0.26	0.6
R^2 (z_{0sim}, obs)	0.91	0.56	/	/	0.28	0.01	0.07	0.5	0.79	0.31	0.25	0.4	0.52
RMSE (z_{0est}, obs)	35.83	10.42	0.33	4.51	0.92	17.85	5.9	5.19	16.97	54.55	51.08	29.86	34.02
RMSE (z_{0sim}, obs)	28.54	10.94	0.33	0.33	0.83	0.29	0.44	6.33	7.93	10.33	24.17	8.33	16.05

Table 8: {Summary of observed and simulated fluxes} Summary of observed and simulated fluxes for all plots, standard deviation on simulations is due to variation of u_{15^*} and z_0 values. F, M res and M no res are respectively the mean horizontal flux over the fallows, millet plots with residues and Millet plots without residues.

622
623 On the fallows, very low amount of sediment were recorded (1.75 to 6.07 kg/m, Mean: 2.94 +/- 2.08 kg/m), and
624 horizontal flux is mostly generated after May when weed biomass has largely degraded (Figs. 12c to 12f).
625 Overall, annual horizontal flux simulations were low ($G(z_{0est})$: 0.0 to 94.95 kg/m, Mean: 27.15 +/- 45.62 kg/m,
626 $G(z_{0sim})$: 0.0 to 0.99 kg/m, Mean: 0.35 +/- 0.47 kg/m).
627 Horizontal flux simulations using z_{0est} for fallows led to strong flux overestimation on F2 and F4. On F2, it is
628 mainly caused by a single event on 13 February 2023 when wind speeds were oscillating around the threshold

629 velocity, due to the noisy z_{0est} time serie. On F4, the stark decrease of z_{0est} values in 2023 due to a change of
 630 behavior in recorded wind profiles amplifies the overestimation of horizontal flux. Indeed, the measured wind
 631 profiles starts to differ from the other fallows after February 2022, as the difference between wind speed
 632 measured at 1.9 m and near the surface reduces, leading to a smaller z_{0est} . The behavior was consistent on all
 633 wind speed sensors for F4, excluding the possibility of a sensor dysfunction. Corridor effect originating from
 634 tree position or obstacles was investigated both on field and in measured data but no conclusive explanation
 635 was found.

636 Despite these incidents, accurate simulations are obtained for F1, F2 and F3 after April 2023 with z_{0est} (Figs.
 637 12c to 12e).

638 Horizontal fluxes simulated with z_{0sim} were not affected by this issue and were in good agreement with recorded
 639 fluxes, albeit slightly underestimated. Fluxes generated with z_{0sim} may also underline the differences between
 640 fallows as F3 is the most generative according to both observations and the simulated flux. The fluxes generated
 641 by z_{0sim} consistently had a lower RMSE than z_{0est} (Respectively for F1 to F4, estimations and simulations RMSE
 642 are : 0.33,4.51,0.92,17.85 and 0.33,0.33,0.83,0.29).

643 Observed sediment fluxes on millet plots can be distinguished between the plots with and without residues (Figs.
 644 12g to 12j). On plot with residues (M1 and M3), the mean total recorded flux was 42.58 +/- 26.85 kg/m from
 645 February to July 2024, while on plots where residues were harvested (M2 and M4), the mean total recorded flux
 646 was 157.6 +/- 16.67 kg/m during the same period. The overall flux was mostly generated between the end of
 647 February and early March and then from April until June. Each of our simulations accurately represents the
 648 temporal dynamic of wind erosion on the millet plots. All simulations successfully model larger horizontal
 649 fluxes for plots without residues (Mean factor of increase for z_{0est} : 1.6, Mean factor of increase for z_{0sim} : 4.6,
 650 Mean factor of increase for recorded fluxes: 3.7).

651
 652 For millet plots without residues, fluxes are mostly accurately modeled by each simulation (Mean fluxes for
 653 plots without residues $G(z_{0est})$: 342.23 +/- 113.83 kg/m, $G(z_{0sim})$: 156.78 +/- 66.22 kg/m) though with a large
 654 uncertainty depending on z_{0s} and u_{LS*} values. Horizontal flux simulated with z_{0est} tends to be overestimated for
 655 both M2 and M4. For horizontal flux generated with z_{0sim} , erosive events during the February-March period are
 656 overestimated and erosive events after April are underestimated, compared to observations.

657 The February-March erosive event on M4 is strongly overestimated in both simulations. Strong harmattan winds
 658 (40°, northeastern winds) were blowing during this event and was coincidental to strong decrease of z_0 value
 659 for z_{0obs} .

660 For millet plots with residues, simulations are less accurate, either because of flux underestimation for M1
 661 (Recorded: 61.57 +/- 11.69 kg/m, $G(z_{0est})$: 14.46 +/- 24.08 kg/m, $G(z_{0sim})$: 0.75 +/- 9.74 kg/m) or overestimation
 662 for M3 (Recorded: 23.59 +/- 3.06 kg/m, $G(z_{0est})$: 415.36 +/- 116.04 kg/m, $G(z_{0sim})$: 66.72 +/- 61.67 kg/m).
 663 While for M1, both simulated fluxes remain in the same order of magnitude as the recorded flux, M3 is very
 664 strongly overestimated by the z_{0est} serie and by z_{0sim} in a lesser way.

665
 666 Comparison between land uses and managements is available in Table 9. Both observed and simulated fluxes
 667 rank land uses and managements G_{DUP} from most “erosive” for a bare surface (2.45-3.40) to least “erosive” for
 668 fallows (0.01-0.47).

Land use / Management:	Baresoil	Groundnut	Millet (without residues)	Millet (with residues)	Fallows
G_{DUP} , sand trap measures	2.45	1.37	0.97	0.26	0.05
G_{DUP} , z_{0est}	2.97	1.81	2.10	1.32	0.47
G_{DUP} , z_{0sim}	3.40	0.87	0.96	0.21	0.01

Table 9 : $\{G_{DUP}$ comparison for observation and simulations}

669

670 4. Discussion

671

672 4.1. Effect of land uses and land management on the horizontal flux

673

674 We found clear difference in generated horizontal flux for each type of land uses. The following land use
675 classification in ascending order of yearly horizontal flux was found: Fallows (2.96 +/- 1.91 kg/m) < Millet
676 (100.09 +/- 68.87 kg/m) < Groundnut (194.34 +/- 56.19 kg/m) < Bare soil (538.70 +/- 62.14 kg/m).

677

678 These results are consistent with the literature as we expect cropland to produce more horizontal flux than
679 fallows, as already observed in southwestern Niger (Rajot, 2001; Abdourhamane Touré et al., 2011; 2019).
680 Absolute values are significantly lower than similar studies conducted in western Niger (209 to 601 kg/m/yr,
681 Rajot et al., 2001; 269 to 619 kg/m/yr, Abdourhamane Touré et al., 2011) and southeastern Niger (368 to 2902
682 kg/m/yr, Abdourhamane Touré et al., 2019). This difference in horizontal flux intensity is caused by a difference
683 in wind erosion seasonality, as a large additional part of the flux is generated during the onset of the monsoon
684 in Central and Eastern Sahel with strong MCS winds. While dry season winds are similar in central Sahel and
685 Senegal, MCS winds are less intense over Senegal causing most of the erosion to happen between January and
686 May (Pierre et al., 2023).

687 For groundnut crops, it is to our knowledge the first time horizontal flux has been monitored and modeled in
688 the Sahel, despite it being a major crop in West Africa (Havinden, 1970).

689 On fallows, larger amounts of sediment seem to be transported on recent, unprotected (no litter cover from
690 previous crop residues) fallows (F3) compared to recent and protected (millet residues left on the fallow) fallows
691 (F1), older fallows with a heavy presence of bushes (F2) or trees (F3). Because recorded fluxes were very low
692 for all cases, it is challenging to measure the impact of woody vegetation on the horizontal flux. However, it
693 seems that bush phenology allowed the observed z_0 value to stay stable from October until January while it
694 decreased on other fallows, as *guiera senegalensis* leaves stay green until that period. This also played a role in
695 the vegetation cover of the fallows (not shown).

696

697 On our millet plots, residues left on field ranged from 400 to 650 kg.ha⁻¹ at the end of November (first dry
698 season measure) and 170 to 270 kg.ha⁻¹ in mid-June 2024. On all fields, weeds represented another cover of
699 around 300 kg.ha⁻¹ at the end of November but rapidly decreased below 100 kg.ha⁻¹ in February. Millet plots
700 response to wind erosion is mostly affected by the presence of millet residues, as the horizontal flux increased
701 by a factor of 3.8 in the absence of millet residues. It has been shown that a low cover of residue (around 100
702 kg.ha⁻¹) is enough to reduce the horizontal flux by a factor of 4 in western Niger, and that a quantity of around
703 800 kg.ha⁻¹ of crop residues after harvest would be needed in order to remain over the 100 kg.ha⁻¹ threshold at
704 the end of the dry season (Abdourhamane Touré et al., 2019) which is consistent with what our study finds.

705 Other studies on the effect of removing millet residues showed that residue harvesting led to increases of the
706 horizontal flux ranging from a factor of 1.5 to 4 in horizontal flux in Sahelian context (Sterk and Spaan, 1997;
707 Abdourhamane Touré et al., 2011; Pierre et al., 2018). Soil erodible fraction has also been shown to increase
708 with crop residue removal in the American Great Plains (Woodruff and Siddoway, 1965; Skidmore et al., 1979;
709 Osborne et al., 2014; Blanco-Canqui and Wortmann, 2017; He et al., 2018) and China (Wang et al., 2002; Jia
710 et al., 2015).

711

712 Recorded horizontal flux on plots seeded using animal traction and intercropped with cowpea (M3 and M4) was
713 slightly lower than their manually seeded without intercropping counterparts (respectively M1 and M2).
714 Because of their development timing (harvested before the main crop), intercrops do not seem to play a
715 noticeable role on flux generation, though they could play an adverse role to animal drawn tillage which loosens
716 the soil in the early rainy season. Differences in observed horizontal flux appears to be correlated to produced

717 biomass left on the plot during dry season rather than to seeding or cropping practices. In Central Sahel where
718 erosive events take place at the onset of the rainy season, tillage and seeding practices may play a more important
719 role.

720

721 **4.2. Modeling approach**

722

723 For both z_0 time series approach, the simulated horizontal flux correctly reproduced the distinction between each
724 type of land use that was measured.

725

726 The comparison between fluxes generated by different land uses and managements highlights the role of dry
727 vegetation on flux generation. This is illustrated in the difference between two types of management of millet
728 plots, as millet plots without residues left on field have a G_{DUP} close to other residue-less crops such as
729 groundnut, while G_{DUP} for millet plots with residue collections are significantly lower for all simulations. The
730 value of G_{DUP} for z_{0est} is overestimated for all cases, due to the difficulty of reliable z_0 estimation from wind
731 profiles. This however does not affect the overall ranking of land uses from bare soil to fallows.

732

733 Differences in-between fallows for simulated horizontal fluxes were mostly caused by differences in simulated
734 vegetation biomass, which allowed the models to accurately reproduce the dynamics of horizontal flux
735 generation. Because the STEP model only reproduces herbaceous vegetation, woody vegetation geometry
736 (trees, shrubs) did not have a direct effect on simulated flux generation. As measured and simulated fluxes were
737 close to none (less than 6 kg/m between February and July), relatively high uncertainty remains on the exact
738 result.

739

740 For millet plots, the combination of STICS with a degradation module and STEP led to a satisfying simulation
741 of vegetation dynamic on all plots. Maximum simulated z_0 for all millet plots remain under 0.1 m and over 10^{-4}
742 m, which is consistent with the literature (Biolders et al., 2004; Abdourhamane Touré et al., 2011). The absence
743 of residues on plots increased the horizontal flux by a factor of 1.5 to 4.5 depending on the simulation.

744

745 An additional conclusion is that on top of millet residues, weeds play a major role in mitigating soil erosion by
746 increasing the surface aerodynamic roughness length during erosive months. After harvest, for both groundnut
747 or millet, the soil is still covered by a non-negligible amount of weeds that degrade over the dry season. The
748 role of weeds for wind erosion mitigation in between cropping periods has also been described in Mendez and
749 Buschiazzo (2015) for sunflower and corn crops in Argentina. Modelling this herbaceous cover is thus necessary
750 in order to reproduce accurately the soil roughness and associated horizontal flux.

751

752 **4.3. Remaining limitations**

753

754 Some sources of plant stresses in STICS can be underestimated, which may be the case for water stress, as soil
755 water can has been overestimated in other STICS simulations studies in semi-arid areas (Sow et al., 2024). Some
756 other sources of stress such as phosphorus or anoxia, as well as weeds, pests and diseases are not yet simulated
757 in STICS and may lead to biomass overestimation which was the case for groundnut simulation and in a lesser
758 way for millet plots. The overestimation of groundnut yields was further exacerbated by the crop failure
759 experienced on GN0 in 2021 (Groundnut yield on GN0 in 2021: 0.06 +/- 0.01 t/ha while reported groundnut
760 yields in the peanut basin ranged from 0.4 to 1.5 t/ha, Malou et al., 2021; Sambou et al, 2022). For millet crops
761 simulation, the early development of the plant was poorly reproduced. These parametrizations need refinement
762 in order to be used for horizontal flux simulations in areas where erosion can happen coincidentally to the
763 cropping season, such as central Sahel.

764

765 Another uncertainty remains in the estimated z_0 time series derived from wind profile measures. While z_0 values
766 and dynamic is consistent with what is known of the plot surface for most cases, outliers such as F2, F4 or M3
767 exhibit behavior that do not match with other observations (biomass left on field, horizontal flux measurements).
768 It is not yet clear what affects the wind speed profiles, though wind direction and obstacles may play a role.
769 Even when z_0 time series accurately reproduce the evolution of the plot surface, they remain noisy and can lead
770 to noticeable flux overestimation.

771

772 **5. Conclusion**

773

774 We presented a comprehensive set of data for horizontal flux generation associated with each type of main land
775 use and practices in the Sahelian area of the groundnut basin of Senegal. Horizontal flux measures ranged from
776 over 500 kg.m⁻¹.year⁻¹ for bare soil to almost zero for fallows, indicating the crucial role of dry vegetation cover
777 in between the rainy seasons. We were able to model each case by combining different vegetation models
778 (STEP, STICS) with a wind erosion model (DPM) through vegetation biomass and cover to aerodynamic
779 roughness length parametrization. Our modeling approach accurately simulated recorded erosion events both in
780 dynamic and order of magnitude, as well as the difference between each land uses. Measurements and modeling
781 for groundnut crops in this study are to our knowledge the first one made for this key West African crop.
782 Horizontal flux simulated and recorded on fallows was too low to clearly define differences between practices
783 but results seems to indicate that younger, less fertile and unprotected fallows may be more subject to wind
784 erosion than older ones or young fallows benefitting from a crop residue protection.

785 Flux measured and simulated on millet crops indicate that the main driver for horizontal flux in the Groundnut
786 basin of Senegal is the presence of crop residue after the harvest. We found no clear link between cowpea
787 intercropping and horizontal flux quantities.

788 Finally, we found that weeds play a major role in wind erosion mitigation, reducing annual horizontal flux by a
789 factor of 4 to 5 during the dry season for residue-less crops such as groundnut or millet after residue harvesting.
790 It is thus necessary to model both crops and developing weeds in order to have an accurate representation of the
791 soil cover and resulting horizontal flux.

792 The modelling approach produces reliable results, capable of reproducing the impacts of both between land uses
793 and land managements for the main types of agropastoral practices in Western Sahel.

794 Following steps will consist in recreating time series of the impact of different agropastoral pathways of the
795 Senegalese groundnut basin on flux generation during the last 60 years, as well as describing inter-plot balance
796 of fluxes in order to increase the scale of modelling.

797

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803

804 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

805

806 **Paul-Alain Raynal** : Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & editing,
807 Data curation, Formal Analysis, Software, Visualization. **Jean-Louis Rajot** : Writing – Review & editing,
808 Supervision, Data curation, Investigation. **Béatrice Marticorena** : Writing – Review & editing, Supervision,
809 Methodology. **Abdourahmane Tall** : Data curation, Investigation. **Baptiste Lemaire** : Data Curation,
810 Resources. **Jean-Alain Civil** : Software. **Diouma Cor Fall** : Project Administration. **Seraphin Dorego** : Project
811 Administration. **Ibrahima Sarr** : Project Administration , Resources. **Issa Faye** : Project Administration.

812 **Ambre Emmendoerffer** : Software, Data curation. **Henri Guillaume** : Software, Data curation. **Christel**
813 **Bouet** : Data curation, Supervision, Writing – Review & editing. **François Affholder** : Software, Data Curation.
814 **Babacar Faye** : Software, Data Curation. **Caroline Pierre** : Writing – Review & editing, Supervision, Project
815 Administration, Conceptualization, Methodology, Funding acquisition.

816

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821

822 **Declaration of competing interest :**

823

824 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could
825 have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

826

827 **Data availability :**

828

829 Data will be made available at request to the corresponding author.

Appendix A. Vegetation measurements details

Plot	Frequency of non-destructive sampling	Sampling size	Sampling category	Frequency of destructive sampling (rainy season/dry season)	Sampling size	Sampling categories	Max mean total biomass (kg/ha)
Groundnut (2021)	18 measures between aug and nov 2021 for groundnut	1 m ² * 8	Height	15 measures between aug and nov 2021, 9 measures of weed biomass during dry season	1m ² * 8	Groundnut (roots, stems, leaves, flowers, pods) Total herbaceous vegetation	678
Fallows (2022)	Weekly	2*1.5m ² * 25 for each plot	Height, cover (photography), trampling	Monthly	1 m ² * 5	Millet residues (from the previous year), green herbaceous vegetation, dry herbaceous standing vegetation, dry herbaceous litter	811
Millet (2023)	Weekly	1.8*0.9 m ² * 28 for each plot	Height, cover (photography), trampling	Every two weeks / monthly	1.8*0.9 m ² * 6	Millet (leaves, stems, cobs), cowpea (leaves, stems, pods), weeds (green, dry), residues	2040

0 *Tableau A.1. : Vegetation measurements details*

1

2 **Appendix B. Groundnut parametrization**

3 STICS' groundnut parametrization is a parametrization of the short-cycle Fleur 11 variety (90-100 days) which
4 is representative of other short-cycle varieties that are mainly used in the groundnut basin. The calibration is
5 based on a set of 65 experiments (35 for calibration et 30 for evaluation) on 3 sites (Bambey, Nioro, Niakhar)
6 in the groundnut basin and multiple years and types of practices.

7 The model already proved to be able to simulate legume's nitrogen fixation (Falconnier et al., 2019, Traoré et
8 al., 2022) and a prototype of groundnut parametrization in STICS based on the calibration of other models
9 (Ricome et al., 2017, Naab et al. 2004) and experimental measures in Senegal (Agbohessou et al., 2022) was
10 the base used for the calibration. Following the methodology described in Falconnier et al., 2019, calibration
11 was made through literature review, parameter determination from experimental data and optimization (manual
12 calibration). Finally, 37 parameters were fixed (9 through literature review, 3 from field measurements and 25
13 from manual calibration), describing plant phenology, biomass development, yield formation, and nitrogen
14 fixation and uptake.

15 Measurements of LAI, aboveground and fruit biomass, and soil water content were made to evaluate to calibrate
 16 and evaluate the parametrization.
 17 During this calibration stage, the model showed an overestimation of aboveground biomass when observed
 18 biomass is low, yet agreed with the overall dynamic of the observations. nRMSE values for aboveground and
 19 fruit biomass ranged respectively from 39.5 to 45% and 38.3 to 51%. High nRMSE values were also found for
 20 LAI simulations, the discrepancy can be caused by the assumption that LAI stops growing after the start of leaf
 21 senescence. Biomass is not impacted by stress during flowering, which does not match the observations and
 22 leads to biomass overestimation in water-stressed conditions. This calibration led nonetheless to a satisfying
 23 agreement between observed and simulated parameters, as well as an accurate representation of the plant
 24 phenology.

25 **Appendix C. Dry module for STICS**

26 While the STEP model provides an accurate simulation of degrading herbaceous vegetation, the STICS model
 27 handles the crop from sowing to harvest. To model the degradation of millet residues left on the plot, a dry
 28 vegetation submodel is added to STICS, based on the addition of the same submodel on the SARRAH model
 29 (Pierre et al., 2015). The dry vegetation submodel describes the decay of standing millet residues caused by
 30 herbivory and climatic factors (decomposition, abrasion). It also deals with the transformation of standing
 31 vegetation into litter caused by wind and trampling. Finally, litter decay is also modeled through herbivory,
 32 burying through trampling and decomposition.

33 Because this submodel treats differently stem biomass from leaves biomass and STICS does not accurately
 34 separate the two, the final aboveground biomass minus the harvested organs is manually separated into two
 35 compartments:

$$37 \quad B_{standing,leaves}(t = 0) = (B_{aboveground}(t = harvest) - B_{fruit}(t = harvest)) * percleaves$$

38 (C.1)

$$39 \quad B_{standing,stems}(t = 0) = (B_{aboveground}(t = harvest) - B_{fruit}(t = harvest)) * (1 - percleaves)$$

40 (C.2)

41 Where percleaves = 0.4, based on observations at harvest for millet.

42 Then the degradation is handled through differential equations described in Pierre et al., 2015 :

$$44 \quad \frac{dB_{standing,leaves}}{dt} = -(K_{degrad,up} + K_{trampling} + K_{ingest}) * B_{standing,leaves}$$

45 (C.3)

$$46 \quad \frac{dB_{standing,stems}}{dt} = -(K_{degrad,up} + K_{trampling}) * B_{standing,stems}$$

47 (C.4)

$$48 \quad \frac{dB_{litter,leaves}}{dt} = K_{trampling} * B_{standing,leaves} - K_{degrad,lit} * B_{litter,leaves}$$

49 (C.5)

$$50 \quad \frac{dB_{litter,stems}}{dt} = K_{trampling} * B_{standing,stems} - K_{degrad,lit} * B_{litter,stems}$$

51 (C.6)

52 Where $K_{degrad,up} = 0.001 \text{ d}^{-1}$ is the degradation from physical and abiotic factors for standing vegetation,
 53 $K_{trampling} = 0.003 * \text{livestock d}^{-1}$, the livestock is expressed in Tropical Livestock Unit per km² or TLU/km²,
 54 $K_{ingest} = 0.005 * \text{livestock d}^{-1}$ and $K_{degrad,lit} = 0.011 \text{ d}^{-1}$. The coefficients are derived from field studies
 55 (Schlecht and Hiernaux., 2001; Hiernaux and Ayantunde, 2004; Kergoat et al., 2015), STEP model degradation
 56 values (Delon et al., 2015), and coefficient of litter degradation taken from Abdourahmane Touré et al., 2011.

57
 58
 59

Appendix D. Aerodynamic roughness length simulations and in-situ estimations

Figure D.1 : {z0 simulation and daily estimations} Aerodynamic roughness length simulations (red line) and daily estimations (grey crosses) for GNO (top), fallows (left) and millet plots (right).

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